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Research Article

**DETERMINATION OF THE CARDIOVASCULAR RISK
SCORES IN THE PATIENTS OF RHEUMATOID IN
COMPARISON WITH CONTROLS**¹Dr Muhammad Ali, ²Dr Ghanwa Muzammil¹Qazi Hussain Ahmad Medical Complex, Nowshera²Lahore General Hospital Lahore**Article Received:** November 2019 **Accepted:** December 2019 **Published:** January 2020**Abstract:**

Objective: The purpose of this study is to find out the ten year scores of cardiovascular risk with the QRISK-2 and Framingham calculators of risks in the subjects present with Rheumatoid Arthritis and non-rheumatoid arthritis and the evaluation of the effectivity of the both standards in the subjects of both groups.

Methodology: We enrolled total 106 patients of Rheumatoid Arthritis and 106 Non- Rheumatoid Arthritis patients with match in age and sex in the duration of this research work. We noted the information about demography and other data about the parameters of this research work. After complete 12 hours of fasting, we took the five milliliters of venous blood to check the levels of cholesterol and HDL, we performed the tests of laboratory on COBAS c-III (ROCHE). We used the QRISK-2 and Framingham risk calculators to obtain the ten years' cardiovascular risk score of all the patients.

Results: In this study, the average age of the patients in the group of RA was 45.10 ± 9.50 and in the group Non-Rheumatoid Arthritis, it was 43.7 ± 8.2 . The average projected ten years scores on the QRISK-2 in patients of Rheumatoid Arthritis group were $14.20 \pm 17.10\%$ and in the patients of Non- Rheumatoid Arthritis group were $13.20 \pm 19\%$. The average ten years CVD risk scores with the Framingham risk calculator were $12.90 \pm 10.40\%$ in the RA group and $8.90 \pm 8.70\%$ in the Non- Rheumatoid Arthritis group. In the RA group QRISK-2 (24.50%) and FRS (31.10%) patients with projected scores were in the category of high risk. We observed the maximum scores of agreement between two calculators in the subjects.

Conclusion: RISK-2 calculator for risk measurement is highly appropriate as it takes many factors as ethnicity, Rheumatoid Arthritis, cardiovascular diseases and atrial fibrillation for the assessment of risk scores.

KEYWORDS: Cardiovascular, QRISK-2, Rheumatoid Arthritis, Framingham, Risk Factors, Laboratory.

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INTRODUCTION:

Rheumatoid Arthritis is very frequent inflammatory arthritis influencing 0.50% to 1.0% of general public in the whole world [1]. Various research works have recorded enhanced rate of morbidity as well as mortality in rheumatoid arthritis, in one research from Canada, it was discovered that patients of Rheumatoid Arthritis were present with median survival seventeen years lesser than proposed general public [2]. IHD (Ischemic Heart Disease) and failure of the heart are the most important reason of death in the patients of Rheumatoid Arthritis. Rheumatoid Arthritis can appear an important risk factor for IHD same to DM (Diabetes Mellitus) [3]. The rates of unidentified HTN, raised LDL and Type-2 diabetes are very high in Rheumatoid Arthritis patients [4]. At one time it was considered about the AT (Atherosclerosis) that it was a degenerative disease which was the result of aging. But recent research confirmed that it is not degenerative or due to aging. The participation of both humoral and cellular immune mechanisms are the participants in the start and the development of the AT [5].

In RA patients, severity of disease, inflammatory markers, and seropositivity of RF (Rheumatoid Factor), seem to have association with the later AT development. Some other non-conventional risk factors may add to the cardiovascular risks and comprise the impacts for long term of NSAID (Non-Steroidal Anti-Inflammatory Drug) therapy and the utilization of the COX-2 (Cyclo-Oxygenase-2) inhibitors, no physical activity, corticosteroids and enhanced occurrence of the MS (Metabolic Syndrome) in the patients of RA (6-80). Suppression for long term of the systemic inflammatory response should be effectual in decreasing the danger of CHD (9). There are many advantages of the estimation of the total risk of CVD and its treatment like the identification of the preventive efforts and the prevention of the relative side effects [10].

METHODOLOGY:

This was a transverse comparative research work carried out in Qazi Hussain Ahmad Medical Complex, Nowshera from March 2018 to March 2019. The size of the samples in both groups was 106 separating into Rheumatoid Arthritis and Non-Rheumatoid Arthritis group. Ethical committee of

the hospital gave the permission to conduct this research work. All the samples were with matched age and sex in both groups. We enrolled the patients of both groups from the OPDs. We used the rheumatology standard of the American college for the diagnosis of the Rheumatoid Arthritis. We ascertained that there was no CVD event among the participants of this research work in the past. The patients present with the Sero-negativity of Rheumatoid Arthritis and with other disorders of tissues were not the part of this research work. We took the detail description of the demography, rhythm of pulse rate, duration of Rheumatoid Arthritis and habit of cigarette smoking. We calculated the BMI of all the patients. We measured the BP of every patient three time on different occasions in sitting position. We also noted the used medicines by our participants.

We also recorded the information about DM and its medication. We recorded the past angina history, MI in close family members, diagnosed the atrial fibrillation on the basis of pulse irregularity with conformation from electrocardiography. We used the standard methods for staging the CKD grade. We carried out the biological tests after twelve hours of fasting. We took the blood samples for the calculation of the level of serum cholesterol, HDL, urea and levels of creatinine. We used the risk scores with the utilization of QRISK-2 and FRS scales. SPSS V. 22 was in use for the statistical analysis of the collected information. We used the Chi-square test for the comparison of the two groups. We used the statistics of Cohen's Kappa for the determination of the agreement between both calculators.

RESULTS:

This research work showed that female patients outnumbered the male patients with 81.10% (n: 86) in both groups; Rheumatoid Arthritis and Non-Rheumatoid Arthritis. The male patients were 18.90 (n: 20) in both groups. There was high amount of the patients with positive past history of MI (Myocardial Infarction) in the family; they were 35.80% (n: 38) in the group of Rheumatoid Arthritis as compared to the 15.10% (n: 16) in Non- Rheumatoid Arthritis group. The group of Non- Rheumatoid Arthritis displayed high amount of the patients present with CKD 10.40% (n: 11) as compared to the patients of Rheumatoid Arthritis Group with 1.90% (Table-1).

Table-I: Comparison Of Risk Factors For Cardiovascular Disease Between Rheumatoid Arthritis And Non Rheumatoid Arthritis Groups

Risk Factors		Rheumatoid Arthritis Group		Non- Rheumatoid Arthritis Group		p-value
		No	Percentage	No	Percentage	
Gender	Male	20.0	18.90	20.0	18.50	> 0.9990
	Female	86.0	81.10	86.0	81.10	
Hypertension Medication	No	82.0	77.40	70.0	67.00	0.0920
	Yes	24.0	22.60	35.0	33.00	
Smoking Status	No	90.0	84.90	74.0	84.00	0.8500
	Yes	16.0	15.10	17.0	16.00	
Diabetes Mellitus	No	88.0	83.00	80.0	76.40	0.2320
	Yes	18.0	17.00	25.0	23.60	
History of M.I in Family members	No	68.0	64.20	80.0	84.90	0.0010
	Yes	38.0	35.80	16.0	15.10	
Chronic Kidney Disease	No	104.0	98.10	97.0	89.60	0.0100
	Yes	2.0	1.90	11.0	10.40	
Atrial Fibrillation	No	104.0	98.10	102.0	96.20	0.6830
	Yes	2.0	1.90	4.0	3.80	
Framingham score	<10%	61.0	57.50	73.0	68.90	0.0110
	20-Oct	12.0	11.30	18.0	17.00	
	>20	33.0	31.10	15.0	14.20	
QRISK-2 Risk score	<10%	62.0	58.50	71.0	67.00	0.4350
	10 - 20%	18.0	17.00	15.0	14.20	
	>20%	26.0	24.50	20.0	18.90	

In current research work, the average age of the patients of Rheumatoid Arthritis group was 45.10 ± 9.50 and Non- Rheumatoid Arthritis group was 43.70 ± 8.20 . There was high amount of the patients with high body mass index in the group of RA with average body mass index of 28.70 ± 5.90 as compared to the Non- Rheumatoid Arthritis group with BMI of 26.10 ± 3.30 . The patient's Rheumatoid Arthritis group were present with high average level of cholesterol of 187.10 ± 35.90 as compared to the patients of Non- Rheumatoid Arthritis group with 179.10 ± 31.90 . Average score of risk with the calculator of Qrisk-2 in the group of Rheumatoid Arthritis was 14.20 ± 17.10 and in the patients of Non-RA group as 13.20 ± 19 .

The average risk scores with the Framingham scale in the patients of Rheumatoid Arthritis group was 12.90 ± 10.40 and in the patients of Non- Rheumatoid Arthritis group as 8.90 ± 8.70 (Table-2).

Table-II: Comparison Of Various Clinical And Demographic Parameters Between Rheumatoid Arthritis And Non- Rheumatoid Arthritis Group

Parameters	Rheumatoid Arthritis Group				Non- Rheumatoid Arthritis Group				p-value*
	Mean	± S.D	Median	IQR	Mean	± S.D	Median	IQR	
Age	45.1	9.5	46	(37.8 - 52.3)	43.7	8.2	45	(37 - 50)	0.3320
BMI	28.7	5.9	27.9	(23.7 - 31.7)	26.1	3.3	26	(24.0 - 28.0)	0.0010
Systolic blood pressure	127.2	16.6	124	(116 - 140)	125.1	10.6	122	(120 - 130)	0.5990
Cholesterol level	187.1	35.9	180	(158.7- 202.5)	179.1	31.9	170	(156.0- 190.0)	0.1170
HDL level	44.5	6.9	42	(40 - 50)	46.5	6.9	45	(40 - 50)	0.0160
Framingham score	12.9	10.4	8.1	(4.0 - 23.9)	8.9	8.7	5.3	(2.4 - 12.1)	0.0010
QRISK-2 score	14.2	17.1	6.1	(2.3 - 20.2)	13.2	19	5.1	(1.2 - 16.1)	0.1220

Both of the scales displayed almost similar proportions of the patients in the category of the moderate and mild risk. In the group of RA QRISK-2 (24.50%) and FRS (31.10%) patients were present with in the category of high risk (Figure-1). We used the statistics of Cohen's Kappa for the determination of the agreement between these two calculators. The maximum scores of agreement between both scales were observed in two groups (Kappa=0.6180 group of Rheumatoid Arthritis; Kappa=0.6710 in the group of Non- Rheumatoid Arthritis (Table-3).

Table-III: Comparison Of Risk Score For Cardiovascular Disease In Rheumatoid Arthritis And Non Rheumatoid Arthritis Group

Group	Risk percentage	QRISK-2 score		Framingham score		Kappa value	p-value*
		No	Percentage	No	Percentage		
RA Group	<10%	62.0	58.50	61.0	57.50	0.6180	< 0.0010
	10 to 20 %	18.0	17.00	12.0	11.30		
	> 20 %	26.0	24.50	33.0	31.10		
Non-RA Group	<10%	71.0	67.00	73.0	68.90	0.6710	< 0.0010
	10 to 20 %	15.0	14.20	18.0	17.00		
	> 20 %	20.0	18.90	15.0	14.20		

DISCUSSION:

In his research work, Cynthia Crownson stated that there was no diagnosis of the angina in the patients of Rheumatoid Arthritis, so there was very less prevention of CVDs [11]. In various countries like USA and Europe, Framingham scale, Reynolds scores and SCORE (Systemic Coronary Risk Evaluation) standards are in use and they do not consider the Rheumatoid Arthritis as risk factor and there can be much debate on the preciseness of these models [12]. The cardiology society of the Sweden gave recommendation that absolute risk scores of cardio-vascular diseases needs the 1.5 factor

multiplication [13, 14]. NICE has given the validation of the risk calculator of QRISK-2 for the screening of the CVD risks [15, 16]. Hilal Maradit in his research work of Non- Rheumatoid Arthritis and Rheumatoid Arthritis groups stated that greater than 50.0% patients of RA group with an average age of 56.80 years, had greater than 10.0% risk, within ten years of the start of Rheumatoid Arthritis and there is very important role of increasing age in the increase of the risk of CVD [17].

In his research work, Mike JL Peters sated that CVD risk in the patients of Rheumatoid Arthritis was

much high as compared to the normal public [18]. Inmaculada Rincon stated that diagnosed risk factors of cardiovascular complications and RA contribute a lot to carotid AT and they play very important role in the events of CVDs [19]. Solomon, Daniel H and Inmaculada Rincon in their research works discovered the enhanced cholesterol level, high BMI level and positive history of MI in the close family relatives [20].

CONCLUSION:

There is a strong requirement to encourage the patients of Rheumatoid Arthritis avoid the inactive style of life, utilization of the balanced diet, participate in the healthy activities as much as possible, leave habit of cigarette smoking and there should be an estimation of the risk factors on regular basis with the help of standard calculators to mitigate these complications.

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